

A Study of the Wayang Play Sudamala by Ki Hadi Sugito: An Analysis of Values and Their Relevance to Contemporary Character Education

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the values of character education in Sudamala wayang play, as performed by Ki Hadi Sugito. Wayang, as part of Indonesia's cultural heritage, is rich in educational values that can be integrated into character development. Using a qualitative research method with a hermeneutic approach and content analysis, this study identifies the character values in Rama Bargawa and analyzes their relevance to contemporary character education. The findings reveal that the Rama Bargawa play contains character values such as justice, responsibility, self-control, wisdom, and steadfastness in principles, which align with the objectives of character education in Indonesia. This study also proposes a model for integrating these values into both formal and non-formal character education. This model serves as a guide for educators in optimizing wayang as a contextual and meaningful medium for character learning.

KEYWORDS: shadow puppet theater, Sudamala, character education, Ki Hadi Sugito

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of social conflict has been a hot topic of discussion recently. The moral crisis affecting today's young generation is particularly concerning. One frequent conflict, for example, is bullying on social media. Bullying remains prevalent among junior high school students, whose target audience is often social media. Bullying on social media often takes the form of derogatory comments (Andari et al., 2023). This is due to a lack of character education. One solution to prevent this moral and character crisis lies in the culture inherited from our ancestors. This cultural heritage is extremely diverse, particularly Javanese culture.

Wayang is one of Indonesia's precious cultural heritages, recognized by UNESCO as a Masterpiece of Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity in 2003. Wayang art is not merely entertainment, but also contains profound philosophical, educational, and moral values (Nurgiyantoro, 2018). As a traditional educational medium, wayang has served for centuries as a means of transmitting cultural values and character building for Indonesian society.

The character crisis affecting Indonesia's younger generation is increasingly highlighted in national education discourse. Phenomena such as bullying in schools, the degradation of manners, weak social empathy, and increasing intolerance are indicators of the need to strengthen moral values within the education system (Widodo & Saddhono, 2015). In response, the Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Education and Culture, launched the Character Education Strengthening (PPK) program, which emphasizes five core values: religious, nationalist, independent, mutual cooperation, and integrity (Kemendikbud, 2017). However, the main challenge in implementing this program is how to convey these values in a way that is contextual, meaningful, and appropriate to the cultural background of students.

One approach that is currently gaining renewed attention is the use of local cultural media as a means of character education. In the Javanese cultural context, the art of wayang kulit (shadow puppetry) has long been an effective medium for conveying moral, spiritual, and social values through narrative and symbolism. Wayang not only serves as entertainment, but also as a vehicle for education, reflection, and even spirituality (Soetarno, 2017). Warty's (2017) research confirms that the plays in wayang reflect noble values that reflect the Javanese outlook on life, and have great potential in internalizing character values through education.

One play rich in character values is Sudamala (also known as Sadewa Ruwat). This play tells the story of Sadewa, one of the Pandavas, who sacrifices himself to save his country from disaster, ultimately performing a ritual purification ritual on the goddess Durga to restore her to her status as Uma. This story encompasses not only heroism but also self-sacrifice, obedience, steadfast

A Study of the Wayang Play Sudamala by Ki Hadi Sugito: An Analysis of Values and Their Relevance to Contemporary Character Education

faith, moral courage, and social responsibility—core values in modern character education. In Ki Hadi Sugito's performance, the story of Sudamala is not only presented artistically but also conveys explicit and reflective moral teachings through suluk (traditional dance), dialogue, and dramatic structure (Nugroho, 2021).

Research by Prayoga et al. (2020) shows that internalizing character values through traditional media such as wayang, combined with appropriate technology and pedagogy, can significantly improve students' understanding and appreciation of moral values. Meanwhile, Prasetyo (2022), in his study of the play Wahyu Makutharama, concluded that character education through wayang (puppetry) has a more profound impact because it touches the affective and spiritual dimensions of students.

Against this background, this study aims to analyze the character education values in the play Sudamala, performed by Ki Hadi Sugito, and to examine its relevance and potential for integration into contemporary character education. With this approach, it is hoped that traditional arts will not only be preserved as cultural heritage but also empowered as contextual and meaningful educational instruments in shaping the character of Indonesia's younger generation.

The play Sudamala (also known as Sadewa Ruwat) is a wayang story imbued with character values. This story tells the journey of Sadewa, one of the Pandavas, who is destined to purify the Goddess Durga to return her to her true form as Dewi Uma (Soetarno, 2017). In the performance by Ki Hadi Sugito, this story is developed with an emphasis on the main character's inner conflict, reflection on moral values, and deep contemplation on self-sacrifice and devotion, which can be accessed through online video recordings.

Ki Hadi Sugito's performances emphasize not only entertainment but also a rich educational dimension (Purwadi, 2020). Ki Hadi Sugito's approach to conveying character values through the Sudamala play is interesting to study, particularly in the context of contemporary character education.

The study of character education has become a primary focus in the Indonesian education system, particularly since the Ministry of Education and Culture launched the Strengthening of Character Education (PPK). Character education emphasizes the formation of core values such as religiousness, nationalism, independence, mutual cooperation, and integrity (Kemendikbud, 2017). However, the implementation of character education still faces challenges, particularly in terms of a contextual and meaningful approach.

This study aims to identify and analyze the character education values in the Sudamala wayang play performed by Ki Hadi Sugito, examine their relevance to character education in Indonesia, and develop a model for integrating these values into formal and non-formal education. This study is expected to contribute to efforts to optimize the function of wayang as a contextual, meaningful, and relevant character learning medium for the lives of today's young generation.

METHOD

This study employed a qualitative approach, employing content analysis and hermeneutics. The qualitative approach was chosen because it allowed for an in-depth exploration of the meaning, values, and socio-cultural context of the wayang performance Sudamala (Sadewa Ruwat) by Ki Hadi Sugito. Content analysis was used to identify and categorize the character education values within the play, while a hermeneutic approach was used to interpret the symbolic meaning, narrative, and its relevance to contemporary character education. The primary data source for this study was a video recording of Ki Hadi Sugito's Sudamala shadow puppet performance, uploaded to his YouTube channel at <https://youtu.be/gAltFLpLDwA?si=WUQD9hKP36X8uVrv>. This recording served as the primary object of analysis to uncover the character values contained within it.

Data collection was conducted through documentation, thorough observation and analysis of the performance video, and the collection of relevant supporting literature, including books, scientific journals, and national character education policy documents. Data analysis followed the interactive model of Miles, Huberman, and Saldana (2014), which includes three stages: (1) data condensation, namely sorting and simplifying relevant information; (2) presenting data in narrative or visual form to facilitate the extraction of meaning; and (3) drawing conclusions and verification, namely interpreting the data to find meaning that is contextual to character education. The validity of the research was strengthened by triangulation of sources and in-depth hermeneutic interpretation of symbols, dialogue, and dramatic structures in the performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Character Education Values in the Play Sudamala

Ki Hadi Sugito's play Sudamala is a reflection of a performing art work that contains profound philosophical, ethical, and spiritual teachings. Amidst the often-criticized character crisis in the modern education system, wayang performances like this present extraordinary potential as a contextual character education tool rooted in local cultural values. The character Sadewa in

A Study of the Wayang Play Sudamala by Ki Hadi Sugito: An Analysis of Values and Their Relevance to Contemporary Character Education

this play portrays a spiritual and moral journey that presents five main values of character education: self-sacrifice, devotion to parents and God, steadfastness of faith, moral courage, and social responsibility and self-transformation. The following explanation of these five values provides evidence that wayang stories have a strategic position in the formation of national character. The following are the main values highlighted in the play.

The Value of Self-Sacrifice

Sadewa is depicted as a character willing to sacrifice himself for the safety of others. When his mother, Kunti, offered him as a sacrifice to save the people of Amarta from a plague, Sadewa showed no resistance and accepted it with open arms. This demonstrates the values of empathy and social responsibility, which are part of the prosocial behavior aspect of character education. Self-sacrifice is one of the highest character values demonstrated by Sadewa. He accepted his fate to be a sacrifice to save the people of Amarta from the plague. Sadewa showed no resistance whatsoever when handed over by his own mother. He even stated that he was ready to accept the universe's decision for the safety of others.

This action reflects the values of empathy, sincerity, and social responsibility, which, according to Nucci & Narvaez (2008), fall within the prosocial dimension of moral commitment. Self-sacrifice is not merely a passive acceptance of suffering, but rather an active action within a spiritual and social framework. In the context of character education, this value is highly relevant for teaching students the importance of prioritizing the interests of others, being sensitive to social suffering, and embracing responsibility as part of a community.

Play quote:

"Menawi punika karsanipun ibu lan jagad agung, kula badhe dherek tanpa ragu. Sadewa mung titah alit, siap tumindak kagem kaslametaning liyan."

Translation

("If it is the will of Mother and the universe, I will follow without hesitation. Sadewa is only a small creature, ready to act for the safety of others.")

This value shows how self-sacrifice based on spiritual awareness can be an example for character education, especially in fostering empathy and social responsibility.

The Value of Devotion to Parents

Sadewa demonstrated absolute obedience to his mother's orders, even though it posed a significant risk to his safety. He also surrendered to the will of the gods when asked to perform the ritual of ruwatan (a ritual performed by a child to provide spiritual guidance). According to Lickona (2016), respect for parents and spiritual figures is a fundamental pillar of moral character because it fosters an awareness of social relationships and transcendence. Sadewa not only obeyed his mother (Kunti) but also demonstrated a strong spiritual devotion to the gods. He did not question her decision, even though it clearly endangered him. He also surrendered himself completely to divine will when asked to perform the ritual of ruwatan (a ritual performed by a child to provide spiritual guidance) for the goddess Durga. This attitude demonstrates the values of devotion, obedience, and spirituality.

In Javanese tradition and Eastern philosophy, devotion is the culmination of relational awareness between children and parents, and between humans and God. Lickona (2016) calls this value a form of moral respect, namely respect that stems from an awareness of ethical relationships between individuals. In character education, this devotion not only forms the basis for respect within the family but also shapes the spiritual and ethical character of students in both vertical and horizontal relationships.

Excerpt from the play :

"Kula pasrah dhateng pitedah jawata. Menawi kula dados titah kang pinilih, mugi-mugi saged nglebur rereget jagad."

Translation:

("I surrender to the guidance of the gods. If I am the chosen one, I hope I can cleanse the world of its filth.")

This devotion not only strengthens relationships between individuals and spirituality, but also becomes a model of how the values of responsibility and loyalty can be formed from an early age.

The Value of Determination

Under pressure and facing an evil force in the form of the goddess Durga, Sadewa chose not to give up. Instead, he sought strength through prayer and spiritual contemplation. Sadewa's fortitude reflects his unwavering faith, belief in divine guidance, and the realization that inner strength is the foundation for facing life's challenges.

Excerpt from the play :

A Study of the Wayang Play Sudamala by Ki Hadi Sugito: An Analysis of Values and Their Relevance to Contemporary Character Education

"Kang maha linuwih, paringana kawruh lan kasagedan dhateng kawula kang bodho iki, supados saged maringi kamulyan."

Translation:

("Most High, grant this foolish servant knowledge and ability, so that he may bring glory.")

Narvaez & Lapsley (2009) refer to this aspect as spiritual character—a dimension of character education that teaches students to adhere to transcendental and spiritual values in shaping personal ethics. Sadewa's steadfastness serves as an example for students to never give up easily in the face of difficulties and to continually seek meaning in every life challenge through spirituality and self-reflection.

The Relevance of the Values of the Sudamala Play to Contemporary Character Education

The character values embodied in the play "Sudamala" by Ki Hadi Sugito are highly relevant for application in character education in Indonesia today. The five main values identified—self-sacrifice, devotion, steadfast faith, courage, and social responsibility—align with the direction of the Strengthening Character Education (PPK) policy launched by the Ministry of Education and Culture. These values are not merely abstract concepts, but are concretely realized through the actions and dialogue of the characters, making them easily understood and emulated by students.

The value of religiosity is reflected in Sadewa's steadfast faith, which continues to surrender to the will of the gods, even when his life is threatened. This value is crucial in character education because it forms the foundation for students' ethical and spiritual behavior.

The value of nationalism is evident in Sadewa's sacrifice for the safety of the people of Amarta. Although the context is mythological, the spirit of self-sacrifice for the benefit of the nation and society can be used as a reflection to foster a spirit of nationalism among students. This aligns with the importance of internalizing the values of patriotism and concern for others in the character education curriculum.

The values of independence and courage are demonstrated when Sadewa accepts the task of performing a ritual despite initially feeling incompetent. He bravely takes on this significant responsibility after receiving the blessing of the gods. This courage reflects the moral courage that needs to be cultivated in students, enabling them to make sound decisions despite the risks.

The values of mutual cooperation and social responsibility are illustrated in Sadewa's transformation into Sudamala, who not only purifies the Goddess Durga but also heals others and fosters harmony. This attitude demonstrates the importance of individual contributions to social welfare—a noble value that is highly contextual for building a civilized and caring Indonesian society.

In addition to aligning with national values, the Sudamala play also offers a contextual approach to character education rooted in local culture. These values are conveyed through vivid, symbolic, and meaningful narratives—a method that differs from conventional lectures or moral theories. This is the primary strength of wayang as a means of character education: it can simultaneously engage students' cognition, affection, and imagination.

CONCLUSION

Ki Hadi Sugito's Sudamala performance not only presents aesthetically rich traditional entertainment but is also imbued with character values relevant to the needs of character education in the contemporary era. Values such as self-sacrifice, devotion to parents and God, steadfast faith, moral courage, and social responsibility are vividly reflected in the journey of Sadewa, who becomes a spiritual and heroic figure. These values are not only philosophical but also operational—they can be implemented in classroom learning and non-formal education contexts.

Sadewa's character, as a symbol of transformation and social service, reflects the ideal character of students who are not only intellectually intelligent but also morally and spiritually strong. This demonstrates that traditional arts such as wayang (wayang) remain highly relevant for revitalization within national character education strategies. The Sudamala play can serve as a reflective and educational vehicle that teaches the meaning of devotion, sincerity, and moral virtue through a narrative and symbolic approach that touches on the cognitive, affective, and spiritual dimensions of students.

By integrating wayang performances into the curriculum—whether through the development of locally culture-based teaching materials, the use of multimedia in learning, or through co-curricular and extracurricular activities—character education can be implemented in a more contextual, in-depth, and sustainable manner. This aligns with the spirit of Strengthening Character Education (PPK), which emphasizes character formation through an approach based on values, culture, and real-life contexts.

Therefore, the results of this study confirm that preserving traditional cultural arts such as wayang kulit is not only important in a cultural context but also strategic in developing national character education. Wayang, as a learning medium rich

A Study of the Wayang Play Sudamala by Ki Hadi Sugito: An Analysis of Values and Their Relevance to Contemporary Character Education

in symbols and meaning, has the potential to become an effective tool for social and educational transformation if developed and utilized appropriately within the Indonesian education system.

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